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D2.4 Recommendations and framework for FAIR Assessment within (and across) disciplines

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Lead Author (Org)	Arofan Gregory (CODATA)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Simon Hodson (CODATA)
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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons
CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FER	FAIR-enabling resource (FER)
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
IUPAC	International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SHACL	W3C Shapes Constraint Language
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards (historically: Taxonomic Databases Working Group)

Executive summary

This report presents the WorldFAIR recommendations on FAIR assessment and discusses a framework for FAIR assessment to take into account the practices of scientific disciplines.

The view of the WorldFAIR project, quite simply, is that in important respects the focus on FAIR assessment puts the cart before the horse¹: it places the emphasis on assessment *before* there is sufficiently strong agreement within scientific communities about what constitutes good practice in addressing the FAIR principles *in their discipline*.

Scientific communities and disciplines, and their representative bodies at an international or regional level, have an important role in setting good practices and standards for how to make data and metadata FAIR, by articulating interoperability and FAIR frameworks. Some communities are relatively advanced, others less so. Given this context, a priority should be to encourage and enable different communities to express their view of good practice in relation to FAIR. FAIR Implementation Profiles offer a useful mechanism for doing so. Thus, the final WorldFAIR FIPs provide a useful reference and a basis on which FAIR assessment can be developed for the disciplines and communities involved.

This report surveys current activity on FAIR assessment tools and highlights some of the issues that have been encountered, particularly in relation to the practices of repositories serving particular research disciplines.

The report then discusses the purpose of FAIR assessment. After discussing current approaches, we again argue that FAIR assessment should consider community practice and convergence on recognised FAIR standards and technologies. Work with the case studies in the WorldFAIR project shows that the question set in the FAIR implementation profiles (FIPs) can help us to identify this community practice. Rather than asking *whether* the repository or dataset uses (for example) a FAIR compliant vocabulary, the FIPs question set asks the user to specify *which* vocabulary (or other “FAIR-enabling resource” (FER) is being used. This is an important and necessary step forward in utility and ambition and is important for future considerations of FAIR assessment. **Realising practical interoperability demands that we have agreements within communities regarding FAIR practice. Assessments of FAIRness require that we are able to formalise such agreements in a useful way, and incorporate them into our metrics.**

The report then examines means of understanding domain practices. Here we point to the work of the WorldFAIR case studies. The plant-pollinator case study (WP10 - Agricultural Biodiversity) used its FIP as one of the inputs to develop a FAIR rubric and a data review process tailored to pollination and taxonomic names. The Geochemistry case study (WP05), meanwhile, presented a call to action for community repositories and databases to share their FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) in a FAIR

¹ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/put-the-cart-before-the-horse>

Implementation Profile (FIP), to encourage community mobilisation and convergence on good practice.

Finally, after discussing some of the challenges of FAIR assessment in relation to domain-specific and cross-domain requirements, including those of machine-to-machine interoperability, we present the following recommendations towards a framework for FAIR assessment:

- A. **A framework for FAIR assessment should include domain-agnostic and domain-specific criteria. Cross-domain criteria form a third category in certain use cases.** (Technical recommendation; for developers of FAIR assessment criteria and tools).
- B. **A framework for FAIR assessment should take into account the practices expressed in specific disciplines: FAIR assessment should be weighted accordingly and the information should be used to improve guidance.** (Technical recommendation; for developers of FAIR assessment criteria and tools).
- C. **To include machine-to-machine interoperability, a framework for FAIR assessment will need to reference profiles for how FERs are implemented. CDIF shows us the level of specificity which may be necessary to achieve machine-to-machine interoperability. Developments in the standards space in relation to ‘shapes’ and ‘profiles’ provide an indication for how this can be done and direction for future work.** (Technical recommendation; for developers of FAIR assessment criteria and tools).

To these recommendations towards a framework for FAIR assessment, we add two more general recommendations for FAIR assessment:

1. **Funders and policy makers should encourage and enable research communities to develop FAIR Implementation Profiles so that these can be used as the basis of alignment and ultimately assessment.** (Policy recommendation; for funders and policy makers, research communities).
2. **Funders and policy makers should encourage and enable authoritative organisations — those that can meaningfully represent specific research communities — to formalise agreements on FAIR practice, in particular by ensuring FERs are published and that the community curates FIPs to describe its practice.** (Policy recommendation; for funders and policy makers, research communities).

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1. Introduction

There has been a lot of work in EOSC-related projects and elsewhere on FAIR assessment tools and criteria — so much so, that it has even been remarked that “we need an assessment tool for the FAIR assessment tools”². This impression is reinforced by a recent article that surveys twenty FAIR assessment tools and finds considerable inconsistency in their criteria and results.³

The work on FAIR assessment tools has doubtless been well-intentioned and has helped advance understanding of the FAIR principles, while sometimes helping organisations understand what may need to be done to bridge the gap between current practice and FAIR compliance. Nevertheless, the view of the WorldFAIR project is that in important respects the focus on FAIR assessment puts the cart before the horse⁴: it places the emphasis on assessment before there is sufficiently strong agreement in scientific communities about what constitutes good practice in addressing the FAIR principles in their discipline. Scientific communities and disciplines, and their representative bodies at an international or regional level, have an important role in setting good practices and standards for how to make data and metadata FAIR, by articulating interoperability and FAIR frameworks. Some communities are relatively advanced, others less so. Given this context, a priority should be to encourage and enable different communities to express their view of good practice in relation to FAIR. FAIR Implementation Profiles offer a useful mechanism for doing so. Thus, the final WorldFAIR FIPs (see WorldFAIR D2.2⁵) provide a useful reference and a basis on which FAIR assessment can be developed for the disciplines and communities involved.

The key recommendation on FAIR assessment from WorldFAIR is to put the FIP horse before the FAIR assessment cart. Specifically this means that it is essential to encourage and enable research communities to reflect on their practice through developing FIPs. Those FIPs can then be used as the basis for FAIR assessment in that research domain. This message has chimed with the experience of other projects, and a number of EOSC-related initiatives are now looking at how to include domain-specific requirements into FAIR assessment. Notable here is the work in FAIR-Impact.⁶

If this approach is to be taken, however, some additional framing of how FIPs are used to establish meaningful assessment criteria needs to be undertaken. Here, we examine how such a framing might be done, and what other FAIR activities might usefully feed into it.

² Michel Schouppe, EC, Oral Statement at EOSC Lustrum event, Vienna, 19 October 2023

³ Candela, L., Mangione, D. and Pavone, G. (2024) ‘The FAIR Assessment Conundrum: Reflections on Tools and Metrics’, Data Science Journal, 23(1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2024-033>

⁴ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/put-the-cart-before-the-horse>

⁵ WorldFAIR Project (2024). D2.2 ‘WorldFAIR’s Experience with FIPs (second set of FAIR Implementation Profiles for each case study)’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236094>

⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/metrics-data>

2. Current activity on FAIR assessment

There has been a great deal of interest in FAIR assessment. This is perhaps to be expected: once a set of principles is acknowledged, the subsequent discussion around them inevitably leads to a discussion of their significance in real-world cases, which highlights differences between different communities. Discussion regarding how the principles can best be interpreted is unavoidable. This in turn suggests that a framework for making such comparisons in a meaningful way be established.

Within the FAIR community, this led to the development of the RDA FAIR Maturity Model Specification and Guidelines⁷ and the development of some of the initial assessment tools such as The FAIR Evaluator⁸ and F-UJI⁹. It should be noted that the initial assessment tools were not developed as a means of establishing assessment criteria, but to demonstrate that automated self-testing was achievable and useful¹⁰.

The RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Specification and Guidelines is a very useful guide for data stewards on the implementation of the FAIR principles. It asserts that there is a need for consistent evaluation of FAIR across different communities and domains, and thus uses a ‘one-size-fits-all’ approach. It does, however, have some limitations, stemming from the assumptions it makes about who is being assessed. Further, this position dictates that it cannot take into account the substantive differences in the varieties of resources needed by different domains, resulting from differences in the research they focus on. It can measure whether FAIRness exists, but does not address issues around convergence on standards or on specific approaches to implementation to support interoperability at a detailed level.

Other similar and related efforts around FAIR metrics have also been undertaken, including the “FAIR Metrics” work by FAIRSharing.org¹¹ and the Dataset Maturity Model from the FAIRPlus Consortium¹².

The RDA FAIR Maturity Model and its kin have enjoyed notable popularity, because a consistent evaluation of FAIRness is something which is of broad interest across the research community. In general terms, we can see this in the proliferation of assessment tools, many of which use the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Specification and Guidelines or similar criteria. This is not the place to

⁷ See Bahim, C., Casorrán-Amilburu, C., Dekkers, M., Herczog, E., Loozen, N., Repanas, K., Russell, K. and Stall, S. (2020) ‘The FAIR Data Maturity Model: An Approach to Harmonise FAIR Assessments’, *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), p. 41. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-041> and FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

⁸ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/recipes/assessing-fairness/fair-assessment-fairevaluator.html>

⁹ <https://www.f-ujl.net/>

¹⁰ Discussion at the 1st International FDO Conference, <https://www.fdo2022.org/>

¹¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata2018118>

¹² <https://fairplus.github.io/Data-Maturity/>

provide a comprehensive overview of all the existing FAIR assessment tools, but we can give some examples to help characterise the broader trend.

Our first example comes from a site published by the Hyve, a group which is active in the clinical research area and is well-known for work with the OHDSI tool suite and standards. The Hyve’s article, entitled “The Road to FAIRness: An Evaluation of FAIR Data Assessment Tools”¹³, looks at four different FAIR assessment tools: Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) FAIR Data Self Assessment Tool¹⁴, FAIR-Checker¹⁵, F-UJI¹⁶, and FAIR Evaluation Services¹⁷. In this article, the features of the different tools are fully described, and the suitability of each for different purposes considered. Is an organisation trying to promote informed discussion about FAIR? Or are they looking for a score-based evaluation? The ability of each tool to provide feedback as well as a numeric score is considered for each tool as well. The article clearly establishes the basis from which the evaluation of the tools is made, and presents a cogent analysis.

Our second example comes from the FAIR-Impact project, which since 2022 has continued work started in the FAIRsFAIR project (2019-2022). They have established a website on “Metrics for Data”¹⁸ which provides a set of criteria, based largely (but not only) on the RDA Maturity Model. Also on their site is a listing of “FAIR Assessment Tools”¹⁹. Listed here are F-UJI, FAIR Aware²⁰, O’Faire²¹, and Foops!²²

This set of tools — F-UJI being the exception — show an evolution in the focus of FAIR assessment. The FAIR Aware tool is not intended to measure FAIRness of published resources against a set of criteria to provide a score, but to measure the awareness of FAIR within an organisation. O’Faire is an embedded tool used inside ontology portals. Foops!, similarly, is aimed at evaluating potential problems to be found in the description of semantic artefacts. It is clear that the state of play evidenced by the Hyve evaluation — conducted in 2018 — has led to a wider set of goals. Both are concerned with assigning a numeric score of FAIRness, as performed by F-UJI, but there is also a strong interest in promoting awareness and identifying specific actions which could improve FAIRness, whether within a broad scope (as with FAIR Aware) or aimed at specific types of FAIR resources such as semantic artefacts.

Some organisations have reported frustration in using the existing FAIR assessment tools, however. These often seem to stem from the built-in assumptions of the criteria used for the assessment, or to derive from the purpose of the assessment tool. One example comes from the Norwegian Data

¹³ <https://www.thehyve.nl/articles/evaluation-fair-data-assessment-tools>

¹⁴ <https://ardc.edu.au/resource/fair-data-self-assessment-tool/>

¹⁵ <https://fair-checker.france-bioinformatique.fr/>

¹⁶ <https://www.f-ujii.net/>

¹⁷ <https://fairsharing.github.io/FAIR-Evaluator-FrontEnd/#!/>

¹⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/metrics-data>

¹⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-assessment-tools>

²⁰ <https://fairaware.dans.knaw.nl/>

²¹ <https://github.com/agroportal/fairness>

²² https://foops.linkeddata.es/FAIR_validator.html

Archive, which, prior to its re-organisation into a larger national entity, was viewed within the Social Science community as an exemplary archive in terms of its ability to promote secondary use of data (this reputation was built in part on its work in developing the Nesstar tools for using the DDI metadata specifications, work that pre-dated the FAIR principles by many years).

In evaluating their data dissemination, they found that they were given poor scores as a consequence of not supporting RDF-based technologies (DDI was based on XML circa 2001). They used the F-UJI evaluation tool, among others, and remarked that it assumed the use of technologies which were not (at that time) common within the Social Sciences community.²³

Another example can be found in the work at CESSDA, the ERIC whose members include the European Social Science data archives. They have performed extensive evaluations of the CESSDA Data Catalogue²⁴, a combined registry of data sets which is essentially a portal service for the data holdings of the members. This has highlighted the differences in emphasis across many of the tools, reflecting the assumptions or purpose of the developers. Further, however, the CESSDA team realised that a key assumption built into the assessment tools was that the organisation providing the resources was both the repository and the catalogue for the resources, something which was not that case for CESSDA. In “FAIRs Not Fair for Metadata Aggregators?”²⁵, the authors describe the frustrations of dealing with the built-in assumptions of evaluation tools which simply did not recognise the class of infrastructure to which the CESSDA Data Catalogue belongs.

Some reviewers have commented that the existing tools also allow for ‘gaming’ of the system, whereby trivial changes on a site, designed to match the assumptions of the assessment tool’s developers, can significantly increase scores while not reflecting any real-world increase in FAIRness²⁶. Such issues are to be expected, and will no doubt be addressed in time; they do not seem to present major barriers to the use of FAIR assessment tools, but rather serve to illustrate some of the limitations currently faced.

Clearly, however, there is a strong interest in FAIR assessment tools and metrics, and the understanding and experiences of different organisations and initiatives has been evolving as more work is done in this area.

3. What is the purpose of FAIR assessment?

Consideration of the different FAIR metrics and tools leads naturally to the question “What is the purpose of FAIR assessment?” There is clearly no single answer, as user motivations vary. Some

²³ Discussions at the European DDI User’s Conference in Paris, December 2022.

²⁴ Shepherdson, J., Papagiannopoulos, K. (2022, December 1). Bulk FAIR assessment of the CESSDA Data Catalogue using the F-UJI API. EDDI2022: The 14th Annual European DDI User Conference (EDDI2022), Sciences Po, Paris, France. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7405623>

²⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/10206399>

²⁶ Discussions at the 20th RDA Plenary in Gothenburg, Sweden, with staff from the Swedish National data Service.

organisations wish to show that their data are FAIR already, while others are exploring how they can begin to implement FAIR, and need help in raising awareness and focusing their activity toward that end. It is interesting to consider where the existing metrics and tools are aimed, however, as this points towards significant shortcomings.

The initial crop of FAIR tools was aimed at providing a numeric score of FAIRness for a single organisation, with metrics based on the FAIR principles understood in the terms of a ‘one-size-fits-all’ frame, as we see in the RDA Maturity Model and other, similar criteria. The available tools and reactions to them show that the feedback provided by tools, regarding how FAIRness for an organisation can be improved, are also of considerable interest, going beyond a simple numeric scoring.

The FAIR-Impact example above shows that there is also a growing focus on shared FAIR resources, such as the O’Faire tooling at AgroPortal and elsewhere. Foops! illustrates a similar focus: how can shared semantic artefacts be made fully FAIR?

But there is a significant shortfall in this coverage of the FAIR vision. FAIR is not only about single organisations making their resources available in a theoretically shareable fashion, nor about shared resources being described in a sufficiently FAIR way. It is also about the *use* of particular FAIR-enabling resources, such that members of a given community can practically use each other’s data. This practical aspect of FAIRness can be described as “convergence”: we all agree to disseminate resources in a FAIR fashion, but we also need to agree on **which standards and technologies** we will use to do so. Until FAIR metrics reflect this agreement on specific approaches to FAIR dissemination, the practical ability to share data and related resources will not be reflected in our assessment tools. **FAIR assessment must, in part, be focused on individual organisations, but it must also consider the community practice and convergence on recognised FAIR standards and technologies within those communities when doing so. Up to now, that additional piece has been missing.**

Work with the Case Studies in the WorldFAIR project shows that the question set in the FAIR implementation profiles (FIPs) can help us to identify this community practice. Rather than asking **whether** the repository or dataset uses (for example) a FAIR-compliant vocabulary, the FIPs question set asks the user to specify **which** vocabulary (or other “FAIR-enabling resource” (FER)) is being used. This is an important and necessary step forward in utility and ambition²⁷.

We can also consider the role played by FAIR assessment metrics and tools in terms of the evolution of FAIR itself. Initially, the FAIR Data Principles raised awareness of the need to describe and share research data. This has had a profound impact on how we collectively think about data and other resources. This awareness has led directly to a broad range of activities exploring how the promise

²⁷ This argument is also presented in WorldFAIR D2.2 ‘WorldFAIR’s Experience with FIPs (second set of FAIR Implementation Profiles for each case study)’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236094>

of FAIR could be realised: organisations wanted to understand if their data were FAIR, and if not, why not. What could they do to reach this goal?

Over the course of the past decade, many different ideas regarding the implementation of FAIR have emerged, and although far from complete, we have a better idea now of what FAIRness consists of, and what kinds of changes to our practice we could make. This is reflected in the metrics and tools now available for FAIR assessment.

In this process of development, we are now at the stage of implementation of these approaches: communities need to agree on **how** they will implement FAIR, together, so that the sharing of data and resources becomes a common, practical reality, and not just a theoretical one. It logically follows that our metrics and tools for FAIR assessment must take these agreements into account.

It must be remembered that FAIR assessment is not an end in itself, but should contribute to enhancing the capacity of organisations to support research, and of research communities to undertake that research. We must therefore consider how to best use FAIR assessment to this end, and take into consideration all of those aspects of FAIR which must be realised in order to practically facilitate secondary use of data, and enhance visibility into the research process in line with the FAIR principles. **Realising practical interoperability demands that we have agreements within communities regarding FAIR practice. Assessments of FAIRness require that we are able to formalise such agreements in a useful way, and incorporate them into our metrics.**

WorldFAIR has demonstrated that such community (or ‘domain’) agreements are generally developed either through ‘standards-setting bodies’ or through the work of infrastructure organisations, which may be clearinghouses for data and other resources, rather than organisations that primarily conduct research. While some domains have formalised standards-setting bodies (such as international scientific unions, like IUPAC²⁸, or explicit standards organisations, like TDWG²⁹ and the DDI Alliance³⁰), others have not. That disparity needs to be addressed. As for the infrastructure organisations, these are sometimes data producers themselves, but often are not: they frequently catalogue the data produced by others, facilitating access to the community’s resources. It is important that we understand the role of such infrastructure organisations: they can be critical to enabling the FAIRness within a domain, even though they may not disseminate data directly, but only provide metadata which describes the data produced and disseminated by others. Either type of organisation may act as a focal point for developing agreed practices, and therefore serve as the organising point of community agreement. The work on developing FIPs for the case studies in WorldFAIR demonstrated the range of such organisations, and helped to illustrate the roles they play.

Even while the importance of community agreements for FAIR assessment was emerging in the work in WorldFAIR around FIPs, similar realisations were taking place in other FAIR initiatives. At the

²⁸ <https://iupac.org/>

²⁹ <https://www.tdwg.org/>

³⁰ <https://ddialliance.org/>

International Data Week in Salzburg in the autumn of 2023, discussions on “domain-sensitive” FAIR assessment revealed that both WorldFAIR and FAIR-Impact were reaching similar conclusions. This can be seen on the FAIR-Impact project website, where an example Social Sciences domain profile is used to help establish criteria for “discipline-specific” FAIR assessment³¹.

Consensus seems to be emerging that while FAIR metrics must be consistent across domains to provide meaningful comparison, in order to provide better guidance to implementers, there is also a need for ‘domain-specific’ metrics based on community agreements.

4. Understanding domain practice: FIPs and FAIR assessment

In order to develop metrics based on agreed community practice, there needs to be a mechanism for understanding what these agreements are. Further, we will need to develop and formalise them in a meaningful way. While the FIPs provide a way of understanding agreements within a community, they were not designed expressly for the purpose of identifying metrics, but rather as a descriptive tool for use by communities to promote convergence, and help develop a meaningful understanding of FAIR within that community.

FIPs ask a series of questions, drawn directly from the FAIR principles, which enable a community to identify one or more FERs which are or should be used. FIPs can be used to describe current practice, or to identify aspirational practice: this distinction is explicit in the FIP. FERs could be specific semantic artefacts like a controlled vocabulary or ontology, a service or protocol, a metadata standard, a system for persistent identification, etc. The type of a FER is determined by its use from the perspective of a specific FAIR sub-principle.

In WorldFAIR, FIPs were used to describe community practice by each case study work package, and were also used to explore the commonality of practice across domains, as input to the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)³². In other contexts — notably ENVRI-FAIR — FIPs have been used by stakeholders within a large domain to identify commonalities, and to promote convergence within the community³³; that is, to identify what community agreements make sense for FAIR implementation. The idea is that FIPs be revised over time, as FAIR practices matures within a community. Certainly this was the case in WorldFAIR, in which many case studies updated their FIPs regularly, reflecting the evolution of their understanding of the FAIR principles, their own practice and the FERs available.

Some WorldFAIR case studies found the current FAIR assessment tools to be useful to get an insight into the FAIR principles, but adopted a different approach (FIPs and related) when it came to improving practice for their research field.

³¹ <https://www.fair-impact.eu/metrics-data>

³² <https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/>

³³ <https://envri.eu/catalyzing-convergence-in-envri-fair-using-fips-watch-the-envri-fair-session-at-fair-convergence-symposium/>

“It is worth noting that there are several good quality FAIR assessment tools available, many of which are domain-agnostic. Examples include the FAIR Data Maturity Model (2020) and the F-UJI - An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool (Devaraju and Huber, 2020). We recommend these tools for those interested in the FAIR principles in general and for gaining insights into the relative importance of each sub-principle. However, our approach in this work is tailored specifically to the domain of plant-pollinator interactions aimed at those who are familiar with the practices, language, and jargon used by researchers in this field. Ultimately, our goal is to encourage data publishing and reuse in the domain of plant-pollinator interactions.”³⁴

The plant-pollinator case study (WP10 - Agricultural Biodiversity) developed a FAIR rubric and a data review process tailored to pollination and taxonomic names, with the main focus on encouraging data sharing and reuse³⁵. The tool is targeted at data producers and involves translating from IT terminology to terminology more familiar to scientists in the field of plant-pollinator interactions and biodiversity. Specifically, the rubric is designed

“to standardise the review process of datasets on plant-pollinator interactions and to qualitatively assess their reusability. In this assessment tool, we provide a list of 11 rubric items, stated as questions, to facilitate the reuse of plant-pollinator interactions data. Each specific plant-pollinator rubric item is linked to one or more WP10 FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) items [or FERs] and associated FAIR principles or sub-principles.”³⁶

This demonstrates how FERs and FIPs can be oriented towards providing information for tools to support dataset review and FAIR assessment that is sensitive to the needs of a specific research field. The FIP formed a vital step towards developing this rubric for good practice in plant-pollinator data. Among other things, it enabled the WP team to map FAIR resources, such as metadata schemas and ontologies, that can be reused in the domain.

Similarly, the Geochemistry case study (WP05) viewed FIPs as a tool for community convergence and benchmarking.

“A FIP is an excellent tool that firstly provides a standardised method for geochemists to provide machine-readable information on how a specific dataset is described and compiled. Secondly, when FIPs become available in the community they can serve as a guide to understanding the scientific resources and technologies utilised by specific geochemical communities. FIPs can offer insights into the FAIR evolution of a dataset or a community. FIPs can also serve as a tool for data producers and data providers (infrastructures), who can

³⁴ Drucker, D. P., Salim, J. A., Poelen, J., Soares, F. M., Gonzalez-Vaquero, R. A., Devoto, M., Ollerton, J., Kasina, M., Carvalheiro, L. G., Bergamo, P. J., Alves, D. A., Varassin, I., Tinoco, F. C., Rünzel, M., Robinson, D., Cardona-Duque, J., Idárraga, M., Agudelo-Zapata, M. C., Marentes Herrera, E., ... Saraiva, A. (2024). WorldFAIR (D10.3) Agricultural biodiversity FAIR data assessment rubrics (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10719265>

³⁵ Drucker, D. P., et al., (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10719265>

³⁶ Drucker, D. P., et al., (2024), p. 8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10719265>

refer to a specific dataset's FIP to provide the information required to understand and (re)use the dataset."³⁷

The WP05 case study presented a call to action for the OneGeochemistry initiative "to engage and motivate community repositories and databases to share their FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) in a FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP). From the various FIPs, common FERs can be extracted to be published ... that will help repositories and databases to become more FAIR (especially facilitating interoperability)."³⁸ This would be combined with a Geochemistry Reference FIP³⁹ intended as a living document and the basis for a future Geochemistry Best Practice System website⁴⁰ which would be modelled on the Oceans Best Practices System website⁴¹. This network of information could in turn be used for FAIR assessment, but the priority of the global geochemistry community as represented in WorldFAIR is to encourage community mobilisation and convergence on good practice.

We can conclude from these examples that community practice can be identified using a methodology such as the FIPs. Nevertheless, we are still faced with several challenges in terms of framing meaningful FAIR metrics for the purposes of assessment. One major issue here is the definition of a 'domain' or 'community'. FIPs give us a methodology which can be applied at several different levels, describing an entire domain, a sub-domain, an infrastructure and its community of users, or even a type of resource provided by an infrastructure. This variety of applications was explored in detail by the Geochemistry case study in WorldFAIR which presented recommendations that the Geochemistry community develop FIPs at the "1) dataset, 2) data collection and 3) data repository" levels⁴².

While there are different classifications of scientific domains for the purposes of funding projects and organising scholarly publications in libraries, none of these was intended to describe the production, dissemination, or use of resources as understood by FAIR. In WorldFAIR, it was left to the case studies to define what their community consisted of, and as a result, the definitions differed across case studies. FIPs do allow for a description of the community creating them, but provide no guidance as to how these communities should be constituted.

WorldFAIR also addressed issues of FAIR implementation across domains, specifically in the work on CDIF. Although no FIP was produced for the 'cross-domain' community as such, it became clear that a different set of agreements would be needed for exchange between communities, as there is less

³⁷ Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R. (2024a), p.22.

³⁸ Prent, A., Rawling, T. (2022). WorldFAIR Project (D5.1) Formalisation of OneGeochemistry (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7380947>

³⁹ WorldFAIR WP05 Geochemistry Reference FIP (v1): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11373659>. The concept DOI for all versions is [10.5281/zenodo.11373658](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11373658).

⁴⁰ Prent, A., Farrington, R., Wyborn, L., Nixon, A., Elger, K., Klöcking, M., Hezel, D., Lehnert, K. (2024b). WorldFAIR (D5.3) Guidelines for implementing Geochemistry FIPs (Version 1), p.10. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10712808>

⁴¹ <https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/>

⁴² Prent, A., Wyborn, L., Farrington, R. (2024a). WorldFAIR (D5.2) Geochemistry Methodology and Outreach (Version 1), p.14. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10406332>

commonality of practice, and thus a potentially different set of FERs will be used to achieve interoperability, where that is possible. The FIPs from WorldFAIR case studies were used to identify where common practice would support such further agreements. In some sense, CDIF represents a more formal expression of the agreements needed within the broad ‘cross-domain’ FAIR community. Defining a ‘community’ or ‘domain’ for FAIR purposes is a challenge which remains unanswered, and arguably is a relevant one for more than just FAIR assessment.

5. What should a framework for FAIR assessment look like?

A framework for FAIR assessment requires that we are able to consistently translate community agreements, as expressed in a FIP, into a formalised set of metrics for evaluation. We can understand that FAIR assessment has two components: those criteria which are domain-agnostic, and those which are domain-specific, as we see in the FAIR-Impact example cited above. It can also be understood that the “cross-domain” case is a third category which will be related to, but may have different specific requirements from, more traditional domains for FAIR purposes. Here, we present the following recommendations towards a framework for FAIR assessment:

A. A framework for FAIR assessment should include domain-agnostic and domain-specific criteria. Cross-domain criteria form a third category in certain use cases.

The benefits of having both domain-specific and domain-agnostic assessment criteria are significant. Awareness of community practice, as expressed through FIPs, should be used both to weight scores accordingly, and to provide much more detailed guidance on how to improve FAIRness. As noted above, an excellent example of how the material in FIPs can be meaningfully presented to researchers has been provided by the WorldFAIR Agricultural Biodiversity (plant-pollinator) case study. The ‘Rubric for the assessment of Plant-Pollinator Interactions Data’ includes examples from the case study’s pilots and in relation to the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) created for plant-pollinator data. This work provides a very useful model for how approaches to FAIR assessment can be aligned and include the important insight into domain practice gained through the FIP.⁴³

B. A framework for FAIR assessment should take into account the practices expressed in specific disciplines: FAIR assessment should be weighted accordingly and the information should be used to improve guidance.

To meet all the practical criteria for interoperability, we may also need to identify not only **which** FERs are used, but specifically **how** they are implemented. This is an important dimension for data

⁴³ Drucker, D. et al. (2024) WorldFAIR D10.3 ‘Agricultural biodiversity FAIR data assessment rubrics’, pp.8-12 (Rubric for assessment of plant-pollinator interactions data), pp.26-36 (FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) for plant-pollinator interactions data): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10719265>

and metadata validation, which — it can be argued — is an important requirement missing from the FAIR principles⁴⁴.

When translating the recommended use of a FER into formal criteria, we may be able to rely on the traditional idea of standards conformance. In the FAIR-Impact Social Sciences example⁴⁵, we see that FAIR sub-principles have been mapped against specific recommendations in CoreTrustSeal⁴⁶. This approach is one which may make it possible to formalise criteria fairly directly, based on the FERs which have been identified in the FIPs produced by FAIR communities.

CDIF shows us the level of specificity which may be necessary to achieve machine-to-machine interoperability. The approach suggested in the EOSC Interoperability Framework⁴⁷ — and taken forward in CDIF — points to the establishment of formal ‘domain standards’ for the exchange of FAIR metadata, accompanied by profiles which could be used to determine conformance. It is likely that a meta-model will need to be developed to support the expression of domain-specific requirements as domain-specific FAIR assessment criteria (and also for helping to realise interoperability as suggested by the EOSC Interoperability Framework and CDIF).

Recent developments in the standards space may provide some useful tools for defining community profiles for specific FERs. Technologies such as W3C’s Shapes Constraint Language⁴⁸ (SHACL) allow for the formal specification of how RDF vocabularies are implemented, and the W3C Profiles Vocabulary⁴⁹ might also prove useful. It is likely that further work would need to be done to apply these specifically to the FAIR assessment case, but these resources suggest some specific approaches to the problem.

- C. To include machine-to-machine interoperability, a framework for FAIR assessment will need to reference profiles for how FERs are implemented. CDIF shows us the level of specificity which may be necessary to achieve machine-to-machine interoperability. Developments in the standards space in relation to ‘shapes’ and ‘profiles’ provide an indication for how this can be done and direction for future work.**

The framework for FAIR assessment outlined here can be understood to form part of a larger chain of activities aimed at FAIR implementation. In projects such as FAIR-Impact, with the “FAIR Implementation Framework”⁵⁰ and in projects such as OS Trails⁵¹ we see that FAIR assessment is a critical part of such implementation. What WorldFAIR suggests is that domain-specific criteria should form an important part of FAIR assessments, and that with FIPs and other techniques we

⁴⁴ The RIPE (Reliability, Interpretability, Processability and Exchangeability) principles, WorldFAIR D3.1, pp.35-42.

⁴⁵ <https://www.fair-impact.eu/metrics-data>

⁴⁶ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

⁴⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁴⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/dx-prof/>

⁵⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-implementation-framework>

⁵¹ <https://ostrails.eu/>

have the capability to develop meaningful criteria based on real-world input from the communities who will use our assessment tools.

While there clearly remains more work to be done, we can begin to understand the importance of meaningful FAIR assessment, informed by community agreements, and also to think about how best we can formulate the needed criteria.

6. Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the foregoing, we conclude by presenting our recommendations for domain-sensitive FAIR assessment (recommendations 1 and 2), and specifically for a framework to achieve this (recommendations A, B and C).

The key recommendation on FAIR assessment from WorldFAIR is to ‘put the FIP horse before the FAIR assessment cart’. Specifically, this means that it is essential to encourage and enable research communities to reflect on their practice through developing FIPs. Those FIPs can then be used as the basis for FAIR assessment in that research domain.

Our survey of FAIR assessment tools indicates that most issues arise when a ‘one-size-fits-all’ tool does not deal sufficiently well with domain practices. Therefore, FAIR assessment tools must consider the community practice and convergence on recognised FAIR standards and technologies within those communities. One of the best guides we have to this is the FIPs methodology.

- 1) **Funders and policy makers should encourage and enable research communities to develop FAIR Implementation Profiles so that these can be used as the basis of alignment and ultimately assessment.** *(Policy recommendation; for funders and policy makers, research communities).*

In the development and use of FAIR assessment tools, it is essential to be clear about their purpose. This includes being precise about what is being assessed (e.g. the FAIR-supporting practices of repositories, or the FAIRness of data sets) and in relation to what entity the assessment is being made (e.g. repository, dataset, community).

Realising practical interoperability requires that we have agreements within communities regarding FAIR practice. Assessment of FAIRness requires that we are able to formalise such agreements in a useful way, and incorporate them into our metrics.

The role of standards-setting organisations of various sorts is essential in setting benchmarks against which FAIR assessment can be conducted. This includes publishing FERs and FIPs.

- 2) **Funders and policy makers should encourage and enable authoritative organisations — those that can meaningfully represent specific research communities — to formalise agreements on FAIR practice, in particular by ensuring FERs are published and that the**

community curates FIPs to describe its practice. (*Policy recommendation; for funders and policy makers, research communities*).

Finally, after discussing some of the challenges of FAIR assessment in relation to domain-specific and cross-domain requirements, including those of machine-to-machine interoperability, we present the following recommendations for a framework for FAIR assessment, as introduced and discussed in section 5.

- A. **A framework for FAIR assessment should include domain-agnostic and domain-specific criteria. Cross-domain criteria form a third category in certain use cases.** (Technical recommendation; for developers of FAIR assessment criteria and tools).
- B. **A framework for FAIR assessment should take into account the practices expressed in specific disciplines: FAIR assessment should be weighted accordingly and the information should be used to improve guidance.** (Technical recommendation; for developers of FAIR assessment criteria and tools).
- C. **To include machine-to-machine interoperability, a framework for FAIR assessment will need to reference profiles for how FERs are implemented. CDIF shows us the level of specificity which may be necessary to achieve machine-to-machine interoperability. Developments in the standards space in relation to ‘shapes’ and ‘profiles’ provide an indication for how this can be done and direction for future work.** (Technical recommendation; for developers of FAIR assessment criteria and tools).

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